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Dual-propelled lanbiotic based Janus micromotors for selective inactivation of bacteria biofilms

K. Yuan,^[a,b] B. Jurado-Sánchez,^{[a,c]*} A. Escarpa^{[a,c]*}

[a] K. Yuan, B. Jurado-Sánchez, A. Escarpa
Department of Analytical Chemistry, Physical Chemistry, and Chemical Engineering, University of Alcalá,

Alcalá de Henares, E-28871 Madrid, Spain University of Alcalá, E-28807, Madrid, Spain
E-mail: beatriz.jurado@uah.es, alberto.escarpa@uah.es

[b] K. Yuan

Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis, College of Pharmacy, Jinan University, Guangzhou, China

[c] B. Jurado-Sánchez, A. Escarpa

Chemical Research Institute "Andrés M. del Río", University of Alcalá, E-28807, Madrid, Spain

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Abstract: Graphene oxide/PtNPs/Fe₂O₃ "dual-propelled" catalytic and fuel-free rotary actuated magnetic Janus micromotors modified with the antimicrobial peptide Nisin are used for highly selective capture/inactivation of gram-positive bacteria units and biofilms. Specific interaction of Nisin with the Lipid II unit of *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria in connection with the enhanced micromotor movement and generated fluid flow results in a 2-fold increase of the capture/killing ability (both in bubble and magnetic propulsion modes) as compared with free peptide and static counterparts. The high stability of Nisin along with the high towing force of the micromotors allow for efficient micromotor operation in untreated raw media (tap water, juice and serum) and even in blood and in flowing blood in magnetic mode. The high selectivity of the approach is illustrated by the dramatically lower interaction with gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia Coli*). The double-propulsion (catalytic or fuel-free magnetic) mode of the micromotors and the high biocompatibility holds considerable promise to design micromotors with tailored lanbiotics that can respond to the changes that make the bacteria resistant in a myriad of clinical, environmental remediation or food safety applications.

Introduction

Bacterial infections represent a major threat in public health, causing million deaths worldwide. In hospitals, the spread of such infections can be very fast, leading to the generation of "superbugs" or multidrug resistant bacteria.^[1] Another important issue is the formation of resistant biofilms in biomedical devices, causing high-risk of concurrent infections.^[2] The quest for novel ways to deal with such infections and biofilms rely on the exploration of new chemical agents and nanomaterials. Their antimicrobial activity can be explained by three main mechanisms: (1) direct release of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and metal ions,^[2-3] (2) direct physical contact^[4] and (3)

photothermal effect in connection with near-infrared (NIR) light.^[5] The combination of different nanoparticles and nanomaterials - such as 2D nanomaterials- with multimode actions results in multifunctional entities with synergetic capabilities for enhanced bacteria inactivation.^[6] Noble metal nanoparticles, liposomes, micelles and 2D nanomaterials can be also used as "nanocarriers" for localized delivery of antibiotics, enhancing both the targeting ability and the antibacterial properties.^[2, 5b] Such strategies hold considerable promise to overcome the increasing concerns of antibiotic resistance by enhancing the overall efficiency of the processes and decreasing the levels of antibacterial agents. Inspired by the promising capabilities of nanomaterials in the antibacterial war, the micromotor community translates the mechanisms of action of such "nanoentities" into moving schemes. Indeed, the enhanced mixing and towing force of such moving colloids can improve even more the efficiency in bacteria removal and inactivation processes.^[7] The myriad of synthetic strategies allow to tailor the micromotor composition and propulsion mechanism for a given application.^[8] For example, zeolite micromotors with a dual Ag catalytic/killing layer shows great efficiency for *Escherichia Coli* bacteria killing.^[9] Such concept was later extended to explore alternative propulsion mechanisms, leading to water propelled magnesium micromotors decorated with AgNPs^[10] or coated with Ag layers^[11] and even light propelled Ag nanostars.^[12] In a more sophisticated configuration, Wang's group encapsulated serine as chemoattractant into Mg/Ag coated micromotors. After the Mg core dissolution, *Escherichia Coli* bacteria was attracted into the micromotor shell for enhanced contact with the Ag ions and accelerated killing.^[13] Besides silver, TiO₂ have been coated in Mg spheres for light-triggered ROS generation for *Bacillus Globigii* spores deactivation.^[14] While effective, the short lifetime of Mg and Ag layers in the above mentioned configurations hampers the prolonged use of such micromotors as well as the removal after treatment. As an alternative, magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles aggregates synergistically generating ROS for enhanced but non

1 targeted biofilm deactivation.^[15] Direct contact killing micromotors
2 compromise alginate coated Mg spheres^[16] or Pd/Ni/Ag magnetic
3 nanocoils^[17] that are able to bind and rupture the membrane of
4 *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria.
5 Photothermal inactivation of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* has been
6 achieved with magnetically propelled spirulina coated
7 micromotors.^[18] Yet, all the above mentioned configurations lacks
8 specificity towards a given type of bacteria, which can be very
9 beneficial for improved inactivation, on particular to treat
10 infections caused by multidrug resistance bacteria. To address
11 such limitations, micromotors have also been used as moving
12 carries of antibiotic, enzymes or bioactive components for
13 targeted isolation/killing of bacteria. Such configurations include
14 lysozyme coated ultrasound propelled nanowires for *Micrococcus*
15 *Lysodeikticus* killing,^[19] antibiotic loaded Mg spheres for
16 *Helicobacter Pylori* treatment^[20] or silica tubes/magnetotactic
17 bacteria hybrids for enhanced antibiotic delivery and biofilm
18 killing.^[21] Red blood cells and platelets have been used in
19 connection with magnetic or ultrasound propelled micromotors for
20 direct bacteria isolation.^[22] Despite the increased specificity, the
21 antibiotic and biological material are prone to inactivation in
22 biological media, hampering adequate treatment. Graphene or 2D
23 nanomaterials such as black phosphorous, chalcogenides or
24 germanane have demonstrated their potential along with
25 micromotor technology in a myriad of applications in
26 environmental remediation, drug delivery or sensing.^[23] Yet, such
27 potential in the antibacterial war remains to be demonstrated.
28 Herein we report on a new micromotor strategy based on the
29 combination, for the first time, of a lanbiotic (Nisin) with graphene
30 oxide (GO) catalytic and/or magnetic rotatory actuated Janus
31 micromotors. Lanbiotics are peptides composed of methyl-
32 lanthionine residues with a highly selective antimicrobial activity
33 towards multidrug resistant bacteria. Nisin is a natural compound
34 normally used for food preservation, which display specific
35 antimicrobial activity towards gram-positive bacteria. Such
36 peptide can bind to lipid II unit of the bacteria membranes,
37 damaging its morphology and releasing its contents.^[24] In this
38 work, we report the combination of Nisin with 2D nanomaterials
39 based micromotors for selective gram-positive bacteria killing
40 (see **Figure 1**). The coating of micromotors with GO impart them
41 with a Janus structure for the subsequent asymmetric assembly
42 of catalytic (PtNPs) and magnetic (Fe_2O_3) engines and results in
43 an active rough layer for a higher loading of Nisin *via* covalent
44 interactions. The micromotors possess adaptative propulsion
45 mechanisms, including catalytic mode (PtNPs) in peroxide
46 solutions or magnetic actuation (fuel free) by the action of an
47 external magnetic field. In the following sections, we will illustrate
48 how the enhanced movement and localized fluid flow generated
49 by the micromotors (both in catalytic and magnetic actuated
50 mode) results in a 2-fold increase of the capture/killing ability
51 towards *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria in raw media (tap water,
52 juice, serum, blood and even flowing blood), as compared with
53 free Nisin and static counterparts. The micromotor strategy
54 display also high selectivity towards such bacteria, as will be

illustrated by the dramatically lower capture/killing ability towards
gram-negative *Escherichia Coli*. We will also show the ability of
the micromotors to destroy bacteria and biofilms. MTT and
hemolysis assays will illustrate the high biocompatibility of the
micromotors in magnetic mode for future biomedical applications.
Unlike previous micromotors based strategies, our approach
displays higher selectivity towards a type of bacteria along with
enhanced stability, prolonged use and adaptative propulsion
modes -even in blood-, holding considerable promise to treat
methicillin resistant antibiotic infections, for environmental
remediation or food safety, among others.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 illustrates the micromotor based strategy for specific
bacteria capture/killing used in this work. As shown in the
schematic illustration in **Figure 1A** and the corresponding time-
lapse microscopy images, the micromotors (both in bubble and
magnetic mode) display high selectivity for specific binding with
Staphylococcus Aureus bacteria. Once the bacteria contact with
the Nisin moving micromotors, a hydrogen bond is formed
between the amine groups in Nisin and pyrophosphate groups of
the lipid II molecules in the outer bacteria membrane.^[24c] The
strong bond allows Nisin molecules to penetrate the bacteria cell
wall, creating pores which ultimately results in the dead of the
gram-positive bacteria (see **Figure S1**). The scanning-electron
microscopy (SEM) images of **Figure 1C** illustrate the successful
capture of *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria by the Nisin modified
micromotors, in which all the surface is covered by the bacteria,
which in some cases displays a flat morphology that can be
attributed to cell rupture (see part d).

Micromotors were synthesized using a recent approach described
by our research group.^[25] Briefly, 20 μm size polystyrene spheres
were coated with a thin gold layer by sputter coating. Subsequently,
the micromotors were incubated with sulfhydryl modified GO for
attachment to the gold layer *via* thiol linkages. The amount and
time for GO incubation was judiciously optimized so a small Au
patch was left exposed for preferential growth of Pt and iron oxide
nanoparticles, imparting thus the Janus character in the micromotor
for directional propulsion (for further details, see the supporting
information). Next, the micromotors were modified with Nisin *via*
covalent immobilization. To this end, the GO layer was modified
with thioglycolic acid to introduce a high loading of carboxylic
acids, followed by activation with N-(3-Dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethyl
carbodiimide hydrochloride. Such activation promotes the
incorporation of Nisin by interaction with the amine group present
in its structure (see **Figure S1** and **S2**). As will be further
illustrated, such modification imparts the micromotors with high
selectivity to interact with gram-positive bacteria. **Figure S3**
shows SEM characterization of the micromotors before (A) and
after (B) modification with Nisin. No apparent changes can be
clearly observed, except for a thicker layer covering the surface
(see part d in the Figure). No speed changes are observed after
modification, with the micromotors moving at speed of over
 $55 \pm 25 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ on both cases.

Figure 1. Antimicrobial peptide modified Janus micromotors for bacteria isolation and killing. A) Schematic of the strategy based on the modification of catalytic and magnetic driven GO/PtNPs/Fe₂O₃ Janus micromotors with Nisin and specific interaction and killing of *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria over *Escherichia Coli*. B) Time-lapse microscopy images (taken from **Video S1**) illustrating the “on-the-fly” capture of a *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria with the Janus micromotors in bubble (a) and magnetic mode (b) and schematic of killing mechanism by specific lysis after the cell membrane attached onto the Nisin modified micromotor (c). Scale bars, 20 μm . C) SEM images of the micromotors after *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria capture, overall view of Nisin modified micromotors captured with *Staphylococcus Aureus* (a), detailed surfaces information taken from the local area of a Nisin modified micromotor captured with *Staphylococcus Aureus* in bubble (b) and magnetic mode (c) and some broken *Staphylococcus Aureus* on micromotor surface (d). Scale bars, 10 μm (a) and 1 μm (b-d). Conditions: 3% hydrogen peroxide and 2% SDS (catalytic mode). For magnetic experiments, the frequency was set at 4 Hz.

The presence of catalytic PtNPs and iron oxide engines in the micromotor structure allow to adapt its motion behaviour using both peroxide as fuel for catalytic propulsion and external rotating magnetic fields for fuel-free propulsion. Peroxide propulsion can be beneficial in remote setting or environmental applications for bacterial removal, exploiting the combined effect peroxide-micromotors. Yet, the chemicals used for catalytic propulsion exhibit moderate toxicity in a long time, which will prevent future on-body applications. The strategy can be extended to any micromotor “chassis” powered by more biofriendly propulsion mechanism. To this end, inspired by rotary actuated nanomotors^[26] and by the magnetic properties of our Janus micromotors, herein we introduce a new concept of rotary actuated magnetic micromotors. As such, the use of hydrogen peroxide or surfactant is avoided since the micromotor only move/actuate by the effect of external magnetic field, holding considerable promise for in-vivo applications. Inspired by previous work and using the equipment available in our lab, we propose a dual actuated Nisin modified micromotor which can be operated by catalytic propulsion and magnetic actuation (bubble or magnetic modes, respectively). For magnetic actuation, a custom-made rotating magnetic field generating device is placed

below the micromotor solution, allowing for ON-OFF stopped rotatory motion.

As the micromotor speed and prolonged operation in solution exert a great influence on the capture/killing efficiency, the influence of peroxide fuel and frequency on the magnetic field upon micromotor speed was evaluated. As can be seen in the plot of **Figure S4**, in catalytic mode the speed increase along with peroxide concentration, with the minimum fuel concentration as low as 0.5 % to generate enhanced movement. For magnetic mode, speed increase along frequency up to 4 Hz, whereas at higher frequency highly turbulent flows disturb the micromotor movement, with an unstable pattern which results in a speed decrease. In addition, for future application, we checked the prolonged micromotor movement in 1 % peroxide solutions. Micromotor speed remains constant after 1-hour navigation in bacteria media. After 2 hours, a slight decrease in speed is noted, which further dramatically decrease after 3 hours, probably due peroxide depletion by prolonged navigation (see **Figure S4, C** and **Video S2**). This fact, however, do not hamper the efficiency of micromotors for bacteria capture and killing, as will be further illustrated. Cooperative motion of multiple micromotors, both in bubble and magnetic mode, greatly enhanced the fluid mixing for highly efficient bacteria capture and subsequent killing (see **Figure S4, D** and **Video S2**)

Figure 2. Selectivity and capture efficiency of the Nisin modified micromotors in bubble and magnetic mode. A) Plot showing the capture efficiency of the micromotors in control experiments and in fortified samples, where: a) moving micromotors in catalytic mode; b) static modified micromotors after 1 hour incubation; c) unmodified micromotors after 1 hour navigation in the presence of free Nisin; d) unmodified micromotors after 1 hour navigation in the absence of free Nisin and e) moving micromotors in magnetic mode. B) Corresponding SEM in control experiments and samples, where: a, b) modified moving catalytic micromotors after 5 min navigation in *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Escherichia Coli* cultures, respectively, c) static modified micromotors after 1 hour incubation, d) unmodified moving micromotors after 1 hour navigation, e, f) modified magnetic moving micromotors after 5 min actuation in *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Escherichia Coli* cultures, respectively. Scale bars, 1 μm . C) SEM and time-lapse microscopy images (taken from Video S4) illustrating the bacteria capture in the samples in catalytic and magnetic modes. Scale bars, 1 μm (SEM) and 20 μm (optical images). Conditions: 3% hydrogen peroxide and 2% SDS (catalytic mode), frequency 4 Hz (magnetic mode); 220 micromotors mL^{-1} , 10^2 CFU mL^{-1} of *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Escherichia Coli*. Error bars corresponds to the standard deviation of 10 measurements.

To get further insights into the efficiency and similar operation on both modes, we performed simulations on the enhanced mixing and liquid flow generated along the micromotors and study the mean squared displacement using 1 μm polystyrene particles as tracers (see **Figure S5** and **Video S3**). As can be seen in the simulations (see A and B, left part) efficient fluid flow is generated along the micromotors in both modes, which further increase the interaction micromotors-bacteria for enhanced and accelerated killing. In addition, the enhanced fluid motion in the presence of bubble and magnetic propelled micromotors is also characterized by the study of the mean-squared displacement (MSD, $\langle \Delta x^2 \rangle$) of the tracers. As illustrated in the time-lapse images of **Figure S5** and corresponding plots of **Figure S5 C**, significant movement of such passive tracers is clearly noted, with dramatically larger MSD in comparison with tracers undergoing Brownian motion. Such fact considerable promise in the dramatically enhanced bacteria inactivation as compared with static counterparts.

Figure 2 illustrates the results obtained in the capture efficiency of bacteria in bubble and magnetic modes as well as the micromotor performance in real samples. To estimate the capture efficiency and the role of enhanced mixing of the micromotors,

100 μL of Rhodamine B labelled *Staphylococcus Aureus* or *Escherichia Coli* bacteria suspensions (10^2 CFU mL^{-1}) were incubated with the Nisin modified or control micromotors (220 micromotors mL^{-1}), 25 μL of H_2O_2 (30%) and 25 μL of SDS (3%) -in bubble mode- or at a frequency of 4 Hz -in magnetic mode- for 20 min. Fluorescent images of different drops before and after micromotor navigation or control experiments were taken using a fluorescent optical microscope and the number of bacteria was estimated via Image J program. Capture efficiency was calculated as:

$$\text{Capture efficiency (\%)} = \frac{(N_i - N_u)}{N_i} \times 100$$

where N_i and N_u correspond to the number of bacteria prior (initial) and after micromotor navigation (unbounded). For additional information, SEM images of the micromotors at the different conditions were also taken. Thus, as illustrated in the plot of **Figure 2A** and corresponding SEM images of **Figure 2B (a, e)**, the highest capture efficiency was observed after Nisin micromotor navigation in solutions containing *Staphylococcus*

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1 *Aureus* bacteria (85 %, both in bubble and magnetic mode), with
 2 all the surface covered with the bacteria. In contrast, low capture
 3 efficiency was noted by performing the same experiment in
 4 solutions containing *Escherichia Coli* (20-28 %, both in bubble
 5 and magnetic mode), as representative gram-negative bacteria,
 6 illustrating the selectivity and targeting ability of our protocol. From
 7 the SEM images in **Figure 2 B, b and f** we can also see that only
 8 a few *Escherichia Coli* bacteria are bounded to the micromotors,
 9 probably due to non-specific electrostatic interactions.^[27] This fact
 10 further testified the selectivity of the Nisin modified micromotors
 11 towards gram-positive bacteria. The underlying reason behind
 12 such selectivity can be explained due to the Lipid II in gram-
 13 negative bacteria is protected by the membrane, preventing the
 14 interaction with Nisin.^[24c] Additional control experiments with
 15 static modified micromotors in the presence of the target bacteria
 16 revealed the role of the enhanced micromotor movement on the
 17 capture performance, with only 35 % *Staphylococcus Aureus*
 18 bacteria capture (see also the low amount of bacteria present in
 19 the corresponding SEM images of **Figure 2 B, c**). Negligible
 20 capture was observed using unmodified moving micromotors in
 21 the absence and in the presence of free Nisin, as also be testified
 22 by the absence of bacteria on micromotor surface in the images
 23 of **Figure 2 B, d**. The high towing force and high stability of the
 24 Nisin probe was tested in untreated juice, serum and tap water
 25 samples. As can be seen, excellent capture efficiencies of over
 26 80-84 % were obtained in all cases, indicating the negligible effect
 27 of sample components in the micromotor strategy, as also
 28 revealed in the SEM images of **Figure 2C (top)**, in which all the

micromotors are covered by bacteria. **Figure 2C (down)** shows
 the corresponding time-lapse images of the bacteria capture
 under the microscope in real samples, with speeds of over $24 \pm$
 19 , 23 ± 15 and $54.4 \pm 25 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ in juice, serum and tap water
 samples (bubble mode) and 20 ± 3 , 14 ± 5 , 41 ± 4 and 12 ± 4
 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ in juice, serum, tap water and blood (magnetic mode)
 respectively. Similar capture efficiencies were obtained in all
 media assayed both in bubble and magnetic modes. Despite the
 different velocities, as already reflected in the mean-squared
 displacement results and simulation results of **Figure S5**, the
 micromotors, along its movement, create an enhanced fluid flow
 which mix the solution and drag the bacteria towards them,
 increasing the overall capture efficiency of the micromotors both
 in bubble and magnetic mode. Such effect can be observed in the
 captures of **Figure S5, D**. For bubble micromotors navigating in
 serum samples fortified with bacteria solution, it can be observed
 clearly how the bacteria move towards the micromotors by the
 vortex effect generated by the tail of expelled bubbles and
 micromotor movement. In the case of magnetic mode, such
 vortex-and-drag effect was evaluated in whole blood, but in this
 case native red-blood cells were used as tracers. As can be seen
 in the capture, a wide density of red-blood cells is present in the
 vicinity of the micromotors, as a proof of such effect, with
 enhanced bacteria-micromotors contact for a high capture
 efficiency. The high bacteria capture efficiency allows for better
 contact and prolonged interaction between Nisin and bacteria
 membrane for enhanced destruction, as will be further illustrated
 for single bacteria and bacteria biofilm destruction.

54 **Figure 3.** Killing efficiency of the Nisin modified micromotors in magnetic mode against A) *Staphylococcus Aureus* and B) *Escherichia Coli* bacteria and control
 55 experiments. Left part shows the fluorescent images of total bacteria (in green) and inactivated bacteria (in red) with the corresponding plots showing the inactivation
 56 efficiency on the right part of the image, where: a) initial conditions without contact with micromotors, b) unmodified moving micromotors, c) unmodified micromotors
 57 with free peptide under magnetic stirring, d) static modified micromotors and e) moving modified micromotors. Conditions: frequency, 4 Hz, 10^2 CFU mL⁻¹ of bacteria,
 58 220 micromotors mL⁻¹ Error bars correspond to the standard deviation of 10 measurements.

1
2 The Nisin micromotors killing ability was first tested by evaluating
3 the viability of both *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Escherichia Coli*
4 bacteria after treatment with Nisin modified micromotors and
5 control experiments using the LIVE/DEAD assay.^[14, 19] Briefly, the
6 assay relies on treating the bacteria with Syto-9 dye, which labels
7 all live and dead bacteria (live in **Figure 3 and S6** for magnetic
8 and bubble mode, respectively) and propidium iodide dye, which
9 only penetrated into the membrane of damage bacteria (dead in
10 **Figure 3 and S6**). For more details on the experiments, see
11 Experimental Procedures of Supporting Information. The results
12 obtained in bubble-mode are shown in **Figure S6**. In the case of
13 *Staphylococcus Aureus*, the trend of bacteria inactivation is in line
14 of the results obtained for bacteria capture. The LIVE/DEAD
15 assay revealed a high compatibility with 3 % peroxide or 2 % SDS
16 solutions, with only 1 % or 3 % *Staphylococcus Aureus*
17 inactivation and negligible effect in *Escherichia Coli*. Similar
18 results were obtained in an additional control experiments in the
19 presence of both 3 % peroxide and 2 % SDS solutions. Also, as
20 show in the fluorescent images and corresponding plots of **Figure**
21 **S6, A**, almost 100 % bacteria inactivation was obtained in
22 experiments conducted with moving Nisin modified micromotors
23 (h), due to prolonged contact with Nisin in connection with the
24 enhanced micromotor movement, which results in highest
25 inactivation percentages. Lower inactivation efficiency rates of 80%
26 and 60% were observed in experiments using modified
27 micromotors under magnetic stirring (f) and static conditions (g),
28 which further reflects the enhanced peptide operation when
29 immobilized in the micromotors. As expected, negligible bacteria
30 inactivation (up to 3 %) was observed using unmodified moving
31 micromotors (d), due to the absence of Nisin. To further evaluate
32 the selectivity of the micromotor/capture/killing protocol, we tested
33 the ability to deactivate *Escherichia Coli* bacteria. No bacteria
34 were inactivated in control experiments, whereas for moving Nisin
35 micromotors, 38 % inactivation activity is obtained (h). This data
36 corresponds with the capture ability observed for *Escherichia Coli*
37 bacteria and can be attributed to non-specific electrostatic
38 interactions that can disrupt somewhat the bacteria membrane,
39 resulting in some inactivation. This data indicates the suitability of
40 the combination of antimicrobial-peptides with micromotors to
41 selectively target bacteria membranes, which can help to design
42 post-antibiotic drugs or to tailor novel agents to treat specific
43 resistant bacteria when antibiotics are no longer effective. The
44 micromotors were next used in magnetic mode for the same
45 application. **Figure 3** shows the experiments of LIVE/DEAD
46 assay using magnetic actuated micromotors under the same
47 conditions. Killing efficiencies of over 90 % (e) are achieved with
48 magnetic micromotors for *Staphylococcus Aureus*, whereas over
49 40 % is obtained with static micromotors (d), further revealing the
50 role of enhanced micromotor mixing induced during actuation of
51 rotating magnetic fields. Negligible killing efficiencies are noted
52 with *Escherichia Coli* bacteria, as also noted in bubble-propulsion
53 experiments. This data further reflects the utility and adaptative
54 propulsion of our micromotors for highly efficient bacteria
55 inactivation in connection with antimicrobial peptides.
56 Bacteria biofilms are also a matter of great concern in biomedical
57 devices and other settings because such contamination can
58 cause severe side infections in short time. We evaluated the
59 efficiency of our micromotor for the inactivation of *Staphylococcus*
60 *Aureus* or *Escherichia Coli* biofilms. The ability to inactivate

already formed biofilm and to inhibit biofilm growth was tested
(see **Figures 4 and S7** for bubble and magnetic modes,
respectively). For measuring the fast killing ability through rapid
biofilm disruption, bacteria biofilm was grown for 24 h in 96 well-
plates (see supporting information for more details) and optical
density (OD₅₉₅) measurements taken to assure that the same
bacteria amount was present in each plate. Next, the supernatant
was removed, and each well was washed with ultrapure water to
remove the free bacteria, followed by addition of 80 µL of Nisin
modified micromotor (or control micromotors), 10 µL SDS (3%),
6.7 µL H₂O₂ (30%) and 103.5 µL of H₂O (in bubble mode) or
treatment using the magnetic device at 4 Hz (in magnetic mode).
After 40 min, the supernatant was removed, washed with
ultrapure water to remove the free bacteria, and the remaining
bacteria biofilm was fixed with 96% ethanol, followed by staining
with 0.1% crystal violet and biofilm solubilization in methanol for
further OD₅₉₅ measurements. Crystal violet labelled all adhered
cells, that after Nisin micromotor treatment are detached due to
membrane rupture, thus the reagent is washed away and the
color in the solution disappear. The extent of color disappearance
can be related to a lower biofilm generation (or higher biofilm
inhibition). The data of **Figure S7, A** (in terms of percent biofilm
generation) illustrates the high capacity of moving Nisin
micromotors to selectively inactivate *Staphylococcus Aureus*,
inhibiting by 70% the biofilm formation (g). Much lower inhibition
rates are noted in experiments with unmodified (e) or static (f)
micromotors, revealing again the crucial role of the enhanced
micromotor movement for targeted bacteria contact and improved
kinetics. Also, unmodified moving micromotors (e) and static
modified micromotors (f) groups exhibit different relative results:
the static modified micromotors destructed less generated
biofilms than unmodified moving micromotors but were more
effective in inhibiting biofilms formation. Indeed, in the “fast”
destruction experiments, generated biofilms are treated with the
target chemicals in a short time. In this case, we envision that the
excellent bubble propelled motion of the unmodified micromotor
may destroy biofilm by physically effect to some extent, with a
“brush-like” effect as previously reported in the literature.^[28] Yet,
for static modified micromotors and since they are confined in a
little area (i.e. do not move along the whole solution or exert the
drag and catch effect), only a small region of the micromotor
modified with Nisin interact with the bacteria, showing such lower
deactivation effect in such a short time.^[29] In the formation
biofilms-based experiments, biofilms are grown along with the
micromotors for a long time, modified motors have more time to
show its inactivation even though they are static.^[30] Also please
notice that such differences between them are not very significant.
As expected, *Escherichia Coli* biofilms were not inhibited due to
the selectivity of our protocol, imparted by the Nisin molecule in
our micromotor. It should be mentioned here that control
experiments with 3 % peroxide and/or 2 % SDS solutions (alone
and mixed, see b, c and d, respectively), revealed more apparent
effects of toxicity on bacteria cells than that observed in the
LIVE/DEAD assay. For example, in fast biofilm destruction
experiments, 1 % hydrogen peroxide and/or 2 % SDS inhibit
about 20 to 31 % of the biofilms generated by both target bacteria.
Such effect is more evident in experiments where both
compounds were co-cultured during bacteria growth (long term
bacteria inhibition). To this end, *Staphylococcus Aureus* and
Escherichia Coli strains were grown overnight. Then 200 µL of

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the bacteria culture, 20 μL Nisin modified or control micromotors, 6.6 μL H_2O_2 (30%), 20 μL SDS (3%) and 153.4 μL LB media were dispensed into a 96-well plate. The plate was incubated at 37°C 48 h to allow biofilm growth. After washing, fixing, and staining procedures as described in the Supporting Information, OD_{595} measurements to estimate biofilm growth rate were performed (see **Figure S7, B**). Hydrogen peroxide and/or SDS alone inhibit approx. 56% of the biofilm. Yet, please note here that the combined effect peroxide-SDS-lanibiotic modified moving Janus micromotors dramatically increase the inactivation rate to over 85 and 95 % in the case of *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria. As such, bubble propelled lanibiotic micromotors will be ideal in water treatment or sterilization applications where peroxide and SDS or other surfactants are also used to increase its efficiency. As an alternative, we propose to use fuel-free rotary actuated magnetic micromotors for biofilm treatment. To further corroborate the LIVE/DEAD results and to prove the utility of the micromotors in such mode, we perform cultivation/biofilm killing

experiments in a similar fashion, as also performed in bubble-mode. As can be seen in **Figure 4**, in fast and long-term biofilm destruction experiments, about 80 % of *Staphylococcus Aureus* biofilm is deactivated, whereas a low deactivation rate is noted with static modified micromotors or *Escherichia Coli* biofilms. Such results are in accordance with the one observed in bubble-mode, except that in the latter case the combined effect of modified motor-peroxide surfactant results in higher deactivation efficiencies. Yet, the biocompatible propulsion of micromotors in magnetic mode hold considerable promise for future in-vivo applications.

To get further insights into the killing mechanism of the micromotors, we performed additional LIVE/DEAD control experiments to check the potential influence of the different micromotors components upon bacteria killing efficiency as well as cultivation experiments of biofilms.

Figure 4. SA and EC biofilm inhibition by Nisin modified micromotors and control experiments in magnetic mode. A) Capability of the micromotors for the fast destruction of a previously generated biofilm (1-day growth) and B) to inhibit biofilm generation by co-incubation of the micromotors and the bacteria followed by 1-day growth. The corresponding plots in each case illustrate the percentage of biofilm formation under different conditions where: a) initial conditions without micromotors, b) unmodified moving micromotors, c) static modified micromotors, d) modified moving micromotors. Right part shows the corresponding plates (stained with crystal violet) used for OD_{595} measurements at each condition. Conditions: frequency, 4 Hz. Error bars corresponds to the standard deviation of 10 measurements.

To check the role of iron oxide nanoparticles in potential generation of free radicals and bacteria killing by radical oxygen species generation (ROS), we performed control experiments using moving nisin GO/PtNPs/ Fe_2O_3 micromotors moving in magnetic mode (b in **Figure S8**) and moving Nisin GO-PtNPs micromotors (c in **Figure S8**). As can be seen in the microscopy images and corresponding plots of **Figure S8**, inactivation efficiencies are similar in all cases, with only 1 % variation. Negligible deactivation was noted for static motors. Thus, it can be concluded that potential ROS generation and PtNPs do not have any effect on bacteria inactivation. In a second control experiment, potential antibacterial effect of graphene oxide was

evaluated by replacing such nanomaterial with black phosphorous. As can be seen in **Figure S8 d and e**, experiments were similar on both cases, indicating no contribution of graphene on bacteria inactivation.

Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) are a core part in biofilms, promoting the generation of a cohesive three-dimensional framework. EPS are a complex mixture of biomolecules, mainly proteins and exopolysaccharides. Characterization of the biofilm is critical to develop and check the efficiency of chemical strategies to disrupt biofilms. To check the effect of the moving Nisin micromotors in the EPS of the biofilm, we label *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Escherichia Coli* biofilms

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with SYPRO-Ruby red dye, a dye to stain proteins. As can be seen in the confocal laser microscopy images of **Figure S9, A**, a high density of proteins with an interconnected network can be observed in absence of micromotors. Yet, after micromotor treatment, in the case of *Staphylococcus Aureus* the proteins can be rarely observed, indicating that the Nisin modified micromotors alter the biofilm, probably via molecular recognition of the linked peptide, which is accelerated by the rapid micromotor movement, as also illustrated by the dramatically lower effects of static modified micromotors. For *Escherichia Coli*, micromotors have low influence on EPS, as almost all proteins remain after treatment. Additionally, to get further insight into the mechanism of bacteria killing and the bond bacteria-micromotor we label the biofilm with Syto-9 and propidium iodide before and after micromotor treatment, which give information about the effect of Nisin and micromotors over bacteria membranes. Biofilm was grown on the surface and rapidly treated with the micromotors. After treatment, aliquots were taken, and images were focused specifically on micromotors to see bacteria attached on the surfaces. As can be seen in the corresponding microscopy images of **Figure S9, A**, both *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Escherichia Coli* bacteria attach to the micromotors, but in the case of *Escherichia Coli* most bacteria remain alive whereas for *Staphylococcus Aureus* all attached bacteria are dead. Indeed, SEM observation of micromotor after long-term killing experiment (**Figure S9, B** reveals that biofilm can grow on the micromotor, yet, for *Staphylococcus Aureus* very few bacteria is attached to

the micromotor, probably due to selective attachment and enhanced penetration of Nisin over *Escherichia Coli*, in which a well-distributed bacteria biofilm is observed on the micromotor surface. Nisin has proven to be significantly more effective against gram positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus Aureus* and corresponding biofilms. Lipid II, the docking molecule for Nisin, promote a high activity of Nisin against biofilm cells. Indeed, the EPS of the biofilm contributes to enhance such bond by hydrogen bonds, electrostatic interactions, etc that contribute to specific binding to bacteria, promoting the further permeation and generation of the pore that ultimately destroy the bacteria. In the case of *Escherichia Coli*, despite interaction with micromotors is observed via non-specific interactions, lipid II is protected by an outer membrane that hinders Nisin to interact with it and deactivate the bacteria.^[31] Once demonstrated the utility of the micromotors in magnetic mode for bacteria inactivation, additional experiments were performed to check the feasibility for in-vivo applications. Several factors such as 1) particle size and biocompatibility; 2) whether the propulsion force is strong enough in biofluids, especially flowing blood and 3) how to track and navigate the particles in vivo, and how to dispose them afterward should be taken into account. To this end, we performed hemolysis and MTT assays to check the biocompatibility of the micromotors. We also check the ability of micromotors for prolonged navigation in blood and flowing blood. The results are shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. Biocompatibility of the magnetic nisin modified GO/PtNPs/Fe₂O₃ micromotors. A) Hemolysis assays of the compatibility of different micromotors and control experiments. Top part shows pictures of the controls and corresponding solutions containing the micromotors. B) Viability MTT assays of HeLa cells in control experiments (1) and in the presence of 20 μm PS-Au particles (2); Nisin modified 20 μm PS/GO/Pt micromotors (3), Nisin modified 20 μm PS/GO/Fe₂O₃ micromotors (4) and 5 μm Nisin modified PS/GO/Fe₂O₃ micromotors (5). C) Time lapse image (Taken from Video S5) of the micromotor movement in whole blood (100 X dilution). D) Time lapse images (Taken from Video S5) of the prolonged magnetic micromotor navigation in flowing blood (left) and ability of the micromotors to travel towards a magnetic field (created with neobidium magnet) against blood flow for future disposal. Conditions: frequency, 4 Hz, Flow rate: 50 μL/min. Error bars correspond to the standard deviation of 3 measurements. Scale bars, 20 μm.

As can be seen in **Figure 5A**, hemolysis assays reveal the high biocompatibility of the micromotors with red-blood cells (RBCs). Please see the experimental section in the supporting information

for further details. Briefly, we incubate the RBCs with water to prepare the positive control. Such media causes the lysis of the cells and the solution become red, with highly defined adsorption

bands at 541 and 571 nm in the UV-VIS spectra. Negative control was prepared in PBS, which do not cause any disruption in the RBCs, thus the solution is transparent and clear, with the RBCs clearly deposited and intact at the bottom of the Eppendorf and no peaks are noted in the UV-VIS. Once tested the control experiments, we incubated the different micromotors and perform the assays. The calculated hemolysis rates were 0% after RBCs incubation with the micromotors, revealing a high biocompatibility. Similarities were noted here with the pictures of negative control. To check the effect of particle size, we also prepare 5 μm micromotors. In this case, the hemolysis rate was 1.4 %, indicating that the reduction of micromotor size might decrease the biocompatibility. MTT assays were also performed to support the previous observation. As can be seen in **Figure 5B**, viability is close to 100 % for magnetic micromotors (both of 5 and 20 μm size); whereas for Pt micromotors 80 % cells were viable, probably due to potential toxicity of Pt. Next, we tested the magnetic micromotor navigation in blood (see **Video S5**, **Figure 5C**) and flowing blood (**Video S5**, **Figure 5D**). The set-up used for flowing blood is shown in the picture of **Figure S10** (for further details, see also the supporting information). A microfluidic chip was assembled in a platform, which was placed on top of the magnetic set-up. Next, the chip was loaded with the magnetic micromotors. Blood was driven through the microchip using a syringe pump at a constant flow of 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Left image on **Figure 5D** and corresponding **Video S5** shows the successful navigation of the micromotors in the blood, at a speed of over 35 \pm 15 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$, holding considerable promise for future application. For future disposal and recovery from human blood, we placed a niobium magnet close to the chip. As can be seen in the right part of **Figure 5D**, micromotors are dragged to the area where the magnet is placed at a high speed and against the flowing blood, holding considerable promise as future disposal and delivery approach. Yet, challenges still remain in future tracking of micromotors in-vivo.

Conclusion

The combination of self-propelled micromotors with a new type of antibacterial agents peptide-based (lanbionics) has been described here for the first time. Specific interaction of amine groups in Nisin molecule with the pyrophosphate groups of the lipid II molecules in the membrane of gram-positive bacteria result in a damage and killing. The strategy does not require additional pre-treatment of the bacteria or sample purification, allowing for its usage in raw complex samples, which is a major advantage over other micromotors strategies based on labile receptors (such as antibiotics or biological components). The presence of two engines (catalytic and magnetic) in the micromotors allow for an adaptative behavior to tailor each application. The main advantage of our micromotor strategy over free Nisin and static counterparts rely on accelerated kinetics for improved capture (as reflected by the 83% capture efficiency percentages of moving micromotors towards *Staphylococcus Aureus*) and prolonged contact for fast inactivation. The adaptative propulsion mode imparts the strategy with a high versatility for further applications. The strategy is also very effective for selective biofilm destruction. The transport abilities of our Nisin-nanoengineered micromotor along with their capacity for intensive interactions and selectivity hold considerable promise to design post-antibiotic strategies or alternative means to treat antibiotic-resistance infections by using

tailored lanbionics. In addition, the high biocompatibility of the micromotors, which also display good operation in flowing blood has also been demonstrated. Future efforts should be aimed to reduce the size of the micromotors and to achieve the in-vivo tracking. Early efforts in this direction indicate the extraordinary potential of IR (photoacoustic) and ultrasound tracking to follow micromotors in-vivo.^[32] Future efforts in our lab should be directed to apply our Nisin modified micromotors to treat bacteria in-vivo, which is a bottleneck in the field of micromotors. The concept can be extended to other more biocompatible designs such as ultrasound or magnetic propelled micromotors, as illustrated by the promising results obtained using the Nisin modified micromotors in magnetic mode.

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Catalytic and magnetic Janus micromotors based on 2D graphene are combined here with the lanbiotic Nisin for highly efficient capture/killing of *Staphylococcus Aureus* bacteria and biofilms. The strategy opens new avenues to nanoengineer micromotors with antimicrobial peptides for effective treatment of deadly antibiotic resistance bacteria.